

18th August 1991

Dear Professor Norah Maier;

“This is just a note to inform you that I would like to participate in the 10th World Conference on the Gifted and Talented to be held in Toronto August 8-14, 1993 to present a paper: Talent - Its Nature, Importance And Nature - From The Standpoint of Neuropsychology”.

It pleases me to report that I participated in all previous Conferences and presented a paper in each one of them.

I was one of the main speakers in the Second Conference held in San Francisco, 1977. The theme of my paper was “Creativity and Brain Mechanisms”.

The theme of my paper in the Fourth Conference held in Montreal, 1981 was “Genesis in Science: A Neuropsychological Approach”.

I received the Plaque of Appreciation from the World Council for Gifted for my paper presented at the Fifth Conference held in Manila, 1983 the theme of which was: “Genesis in Literature: A Neuropsychological Approach”.

The theme of my paper presented at the Sixth Conference held in Hamburg, 1985 was: “Genesis in Technology: A Neuropsychological Approach”.

The theme of my paper presented at the Seventh Conference held in Salt Lake City, 1986 was: “Creative Imagination: A Neuropsychological Approach”.

The theme of my paper presented at the Eighth Conference held in Sydney, 1989 was: “The Genesis of Creative Ideas in Science: A Neuropsychological Approach”.

And the theme of my paper presented at the Ninth Conference in Hague few weeks ago, 1991 was: “The Genesis of Creative Imagination Poetry: A Neuropsychological Approach”.

Best regards
Dr. Nouri Jaffar

August 18, 1991

Dear Professor Morah Kraier

This is just a note to inform you that I would like to participate in the 10th World Conference on the Gifted and Talented to be held in Toronto August 8 - 14, 1993 and to present a paper:

Talent
its Nature, Importance and Nurture

- From the Standpoint of Neuropsychology -

It pleases me to report that I participated in all previous Conferences and presented a paper in each one of them.

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Genius in Science: A Neuropsychological Approach. I received

the Plaque of Appreciation from the World Council for Gifted and Talented for my paper presented at the Fifth Conference held in Manila, 1983 the theme of which was:

Genius in Literature: A Neuropsychological Approach. The theme of my paper presented at the 6th Conference held in Hamburg, 1985 was: Genius in Technology: A Neuropsychological Approach. The theme of my paper presented at the 7th Conference held in Salt Lake City, 1986 was: Creative

Imagination: A Neuropsychological Approach. The theme of my paper presented at the 8th Sydney 1989 was: The Genesis of Creative Ideas in

Science: A Neuropsychological Approach. And the theme of my paper presented at the Hague a few weeks ago was: The Genesis of Creative Imagination Poetry: A Neuropsychological Approach. Best regards.

Dr. Nouzi Toffar
P.O. Box 80 636,
Tripoli, Libya

World Raiser

August 15 1991

president.

The World Council for the Gifted and Talented

Director

50th World Conference

University of Toronto
School of Continuing Studies
158 St. George Street

Toronto, Ontario, Canada

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